

**“A STUDY ON THE JOB SATISFACTION OF IT
EMPLOYEE”**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTER’S
DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK(M.S.W.)**

**ABDUL FIROZ A
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**UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF
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DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL WORK
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY**

**CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR
MANGALURU – 575001**

2021-2022

**A STUDY ON ALCOHOLISM AND ITS IMPACT ON YOUTH AT
MANGALORE**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK (M.S.W.)**

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALURU – 575001

2021-2022

**A STUDY ON STRESS AMONG THE PARENTS AND CAREGIVERS OF
AUTISM CHILDREN**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK (M.S.W.)**

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2021-2022

**A STUDY ON THE PSYCHO-SOCIAL PROBLEMS FACED BY THE
PRIMARY CARE GIVERS OF CANCER PATIENTS IN
MANANTHAVADY MUNICIPALITY**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
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CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALURU – 575001**

2021-2022

**“IMPACT OF ONLINE EDUCATION ON
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL BEING AND ACHIEVEMENT
MOTIVATION AMONG ADULTS”**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR
MASTER'S DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK (M.S.W.)**

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City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru – 575001

2021-2022

**A STUDY ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL
ASPECTS BEHIND ALCOHOL RELAPSE**

A Dissertation submitted to the Srinivas University, Institute of Social
Sciences and Humanities in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the
award of the degree

**MASTER OF SOCIAL WORK IN MEDICAL AND
PSYCHIATRIC**

By,
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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALURU
Department of Social Work**

- 575001

**AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON THE HOLISTIC
WELFARE OF ELDERLY IN MANGALURU**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTER'S
DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK (M.S.W.)**

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2021-2022

**A QUALITATIVE STUDY ON THE ROLE OF ASHA WORKERS
AS FRONTLINE WARRIORS DURING THE COVID
PANDEMIC IN MARARIKULAM SOUTH PANCHAYAT,
ALAPPUZHA DISTRICT, KERALA**

A Dissertation submitted to the Srinivas University, College of Social
Sciences and Humanities in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the
award of the degree

MASTER OF SOCIAL WORK IN MEDICAL AND PSYCHIATRY

By,

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY MANGALURU

Department of Social Work

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**A STUDY ON THE WORK LIFE OF CONTRACT WORKERS WITH
REFERENCE TO FERTILISERS AND CHEMICALS TRAVANCORE
LIMITED, UDYOGAMANDAL, COCHIN**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK (M.S.W.)**

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DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL WORK
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CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALURU – 575001
2021-2022**

**A STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF PRICE FLUCTUATION AND
CLIMATE
CHANGE ON FARMERS IN KUNNAMTHANAM PANCHAYATH,
PATHANAMTHITTA**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
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2021-2022

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY ON YOUNG ADULTS'
ATTITUDES TOWARD PEOPLE WITH MENTAL
ILLNESS AND THEIR BELIEFS ABOUT THE
CAUSATION OF MENTAL ILLNESS.**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
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CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALURU – 575001

2021-2022

**A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE'S HEALTH AND SAFETY MEASURES
WITH REFERENCE TO BIGBAGS INTERNATIONAL PVT. LTD.
MANGALORE**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS
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THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR
MASTER'S DEGREE IN SOCIAL WORK
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CITY CAMPUS, PANDESHWAR, MANGALURU – 575001

2021-2022

**EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND ITS
IMPACT ON RETENTION AND WORK
PERFORMANCE – IN REFERENCE TO KINLONG
HARDWARE CONSTRUCTION**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN
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2021-2022

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON MARITAL
SATISFACTION AMONG NEW GENERATION
COUPLE AND OLD GENERATION COUPLE**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS
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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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5750012021-2022

**WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WORKING WOMEN-SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO INDIAN DESIGNS EXPORTS PRIVATE LIMITED**

**DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR SECOND YEAR MASTERS
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2021-2022**

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